

Vendor-Buyer Collaboration in Supply Chain Management with Quality Inspection on the Buyer's Side

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Abstract

Collaborative vendor-buyer relationships are an essential factor when it comes to successful supply chain management (SCM). For SCM operations to run smoothly and congenially, different parties are required to build and manage win-win relationships. The proposed work investigates a single-vendor and multiple-buyer collaboration with a consignment agreement. Furthermore, the parts provided by the vendor are imperfect, with a certain proportion of defective items. Buyers are assumed to be responsible for quality inspection, which is subject to errors in item classification, and errors are incurred as costs. Finally, an optimization model is formulated, an approach to the optimum solution is developed, and a numerical example is solved. The results show that the minimum SC cost can be achieved if the vendor and buyers adopt a collaboration policy. This policy requires sacrifice from the SC parties, i.e., abandoning their minimum cost under individual behavior to reduce the system's total cost under the collaboration.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management; Vendor-Buyer Collaboration; Product Inspection.

1. Introduction

Companies and organizations worldwide seek a competitive advantage through enhanced engagement with their supply chain (SC) partners. Collaboration approaches between vendors and buyers include quantity discounts, common cycle lengths, and quality inspections (Khan et al., 2014). Furthermore, consignment stock (CS) and vendor-managed inventory (VMI) are efficient approaches for better integration and information exchange across vendors and buyers (Alfares and Attia, 2017; Ben-Daya et al., 2013; Blackstone and Cox, 2008).

The essential distinction between the two policies is that in CS, the buyer is responsible for ordering decisions and expenses, but in the VMI case, they are made by the vendor (Gümüş et al., 2008). In the line of studying vendor-buyer collaboration, (Ben-Daya et al., 2013) concluded that collaboration has mutual advantages for the vendor and buyers because it reduces setup costs for both parties if the vendor has a flexible capacity. In a two-echelon SC model, (Khan et al., 2014) adopted a quality inspection activity on the buyer's side in which parts can be misclassified, e.g., a good item may be classified as bad. Inspection errors require SC parties to improve relationship management, product and process design, and personnel training.

This research contributes to the literature by proposing a framework to manage SC through vendor and buyer collaboration and parts inspection activity. In particular, this work proposes a single-vendor, multiple-buyers SC structure that incorporates complete collaboration regulations while considering the product inspection activity and its possible errors.

The following sections of this paper are organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the state-of-the-art literature. Section 3 explains the assumptions and model development steps. Sections 4 and 5 present

the solution approach and solve a numerical example⁵. Finally, Section 6 provides conclusions and suggestions for future research.

2. Literature review

This section presents the state-of-the-art in the area of SCM under vendor-buyer collaboration. The reviewed papers are classified into (1) single-vendor multiple-buyer models, (2) vendor-buyer collaboration and profit sharing, and (3) integrated quality control and SCM. Within each group, recent papers are discussed chronologically from 2010 to illustrate the trend of interests.

The first group of papers is on the single-vendor multiple-buyer models. Darwish and Odah (2010) adopted the VMI policy, in which the vendor charges the ordering and surplus inventory costs. In the case of an SC with capacity restrictions and contract-specified inventory levels, the vendor is penalized for exceeding these bounds. Rouibi and Burlat (2010) modeled a three-echelon SC under (s, S) inventory policy, and two VMI policies were analyzed, revealing a more significant advantage for less effective supply chains. Battini et al. (2010) modeled a single-vendor multi-buyer SC with buyer's warehouse space constraints as well as risks associated with stock-outs and material obsolescence.

Order quantity size variation has been recommended to improve SC performance by Hoque (2011), i.e., unequal sizes result in a cost reduction. The model has constraints on transportation and storage capacities, lead times, and batch sizes. Furthermore, the author assumed that the buyer only pays the ordering cost once, regardless of the number of orders. Hariga et al. (2013) used an efficient heuristic to minimize the joint inventory costs of a mixed integer nonlinear program (MINLP) if the vendor has an unlimited supply and a lower unit holding cost than the buyers. Ben-Daya et al. (2013) investigated the impact of three different partnership policies: no coordination agreement, VMI-CS agreements, and integration with a single decision maker. Choudhary et al. (2014) found that under CS policy, buyer cost savings increase if the ordering cost and demand variability increase. However, the supplier would prefer the CS policy if the setup and shipment expenses are exceptionally high. Zanoni and Jaber (2015) examined a case in which buyer demand is affected by the buyer's stock level. In addition, the shortage is not allowed and is avoided by imposing a minimum stock level and an instantaneous replenishment policy. Hong et al. (2016) assumed that demand follows a uniform distribution and shortage is a lost sale. They found that a VMI policy costs less than a traditional individual policy.

Zahran et al. (2016a and 2016b) assessed the effect of payment time under CS policy, e.g., on time, delay without interest, and delay with interest. They found that the preferred scenario is a delay with interest. Lee et al. (2017) realized that profit increases as the buyer embraces a minimum reorder level policy if the restocking level at the buyer's side is a decision variable. Hemmati et al. (2017) assumed a linear relationship between the buyer's customer demand, the stock level, and the market price.

CS and VMI are two common policies in SCM; Owusu Kwateng et al. (2022) found that VMI improves ordering frequency, decreases shortage quantity, and lowers inventory cost. Hariga et al. (2023 and 2022) explored the effect of CO₂ regulation policies, e.g., carbon cap and tax policies, on SCM decisions. They found that with minor operational modifications, a significantly lower CO₂ footprint can be achieved at a slight increase in operational cost. Gharaei et al. (2023) assumed the vendor was responsible for product inspection without errors and charged reworking, disposal, holding, and inspection costs. The model was mixed integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) and employed generalized bender decomposition (GBD) for optimizing the number and quantity of shipments. However, the model overlooked the benefits of coordination between different SC parties.

The second group of papers is on vendor-buyer collaboration and profit sharing. Ben-Daya et al. (2013) and Hu et al. (2014) addressed scenarios in which the vendor's or one or more purchasers' costs increased due to the collaboration and provided appropriate solutions. If the vendor is in a worse financial situation, some of the buyers' savings can be transferred to the vendor via a unit price increase.

The maximum price increase is the one that turns at least one buyer off from pursuing the collaboration. The smallest price rise leaves the vendor no worse off than before the cooperation. Similarly, if specific buyers, or all of them, are worse off, the vendor can reduce prices to induce these purchasers to accept the partnership. Avinadav et al. (2022) considered revenue sharing between an app developer and a distribution platform. They found that the platform benefits when the developer knows its signal in which platforms suggest sharing information with developers, such as Google Firebase and Apple App-Analytics.

The third group of papers considers SC's quality control activities and inventory management. Inspection can be applied at the vendor or buyer side. On the vendor side, Chiu et al. (2013a and 2013b) investigated the presence of defective items, which can be reworked. In addition, a failure may occur during rework and assume a common cycle time for multiple items. Jaber et al. (2014a) assumed that the supplier is far from the buyer, making it irrational to return defective items for rework. Jaber et al. (2014b) later assumed that the supplier oversees production, repair, and waste disposal. Two inspection scenarios are considered: on the vendor's and buyer's sides. The model assumes that new and repaired products are of the same quality. Therefore, defective items produced during production and remanufacturing are ignored. Bazan et al. (2014) attempted to solve the problem of imperfect production by considering reworking and interrupting the production run by applying modest setups to restore the process to its in-control state.

Sana (2011) adopted an unequal shipment policy between SC echelons where items are inspected and defective ones are returned to the previous echelon in a single shipment. Khan et al. (2016 and 2014) considered the errors in inspection on the buyer's side and the learning rate on the vendor's side. In addition, they adopted two schemes for defective items: scrape or rework the costs of remanufacturing and disposal of the defective items. Later, Akbarzadeh et al. (2016) studied a more realistic case where the rework of defective items is imperfect, i.e., it may still produce imperfect ones. Hariga et al. (2017) considered defective items that need remanufacturing and provided a model that optimizes the order quantity and the number of shipments for newly manufactured and remanufactured parts. Giri et al. (2017) considered unequal shipment sizes, the buyer conducting the inspection, and defective items scrapped or repaired. Salas-Navarro et al. (2023) assumed a probabilistic demand rate for the customer and a constant deterioration rate for the vendor. The model considers many costs, such as deterioration, screening, disposal, and labor. A vendor-buyer partnership is designed based on sharing information about sales forecasts, operating costs, storage policies, and quality characteristics.

In conclusion, the contribution of this paper arises from considering several aspects, including the cases of correctly rejected, falsely rejected, correctly accepted, falsely accepted, and vendor-buyer collaboration. In this paper, the inspection activity is assumed to be undertaken on the buyer's side, as it is common practice in many real-life situations (Alfares and Attia, 2017; Giri et al., 2017; Jaber et al., 2014a, 2014c; Khan et al., 2016, 2014; Salameh and Jaber, 2000).

3. Model development

This section describes the steps to formulate the mathematical model and the suggested optimization procedure.

Table 9 Model notations

K_{bpi} : cost of placing an order at buyer i (\$/order)

K_{bri} : cost of receiving an order at buyer i (\$/order)

h_{boi} : cost of tied-up inventory at buyer i charged by the vendor (\$/unit/unit time)

- h_{bsi} : cost of physical storage at buyer i (\$/unit/unit time)
- K_{vs} : cost of setup at the vendor (\$/order)
- K_{vri} : cost of order release at the vendor to buyer i (\$/order)
- h_v : cost of holding one unit at the vendor (\$/unit/unit time)
- n : number of orders from the vendor to buyer i , assumed to be equal
- N : number of buyers
- d_i : demand at buyer i (units/unit time)
- D : total demand of buyers = $\sum_{i=1}^N d_i$ (units/unit time)
- P : production rate of the vendor (units/unit time)
- q_i : order quantity to buyer i
- Q : total orders quantity to all buyers = $\sum_{i=1}^N q_i$
- t : time to produce one order = Q/P
- T : replenishment cycle length
- TC_v : total cost for vendor per unit of time
- TC_k : total cost for buyer i per unit of time
- TC : total cost for the supply chain per unit of time
- e_1 : probability of type I error, i.e., a non-defective item being classified as defective
- e_2 : probability of type II error, i.e., a defective item being classified as non-defective
- c_{fa} : cost of falsely accepting a defective item
- c_{fr} : cost of falsely rejecting a non-defective item
- c_{cr} : cost of correctly rejecting a defective item
- p : percentage of defective supplied by the vendor
- p_e : percentage of rejected items, either correctly or falsely rejected
- I_r : buyer's inspection rate (units /unit time)
- t_{si} : inspection time of buyer i (time/order) = q_i/I_r

3.1. Assumptions

- 1) The vendor is responsible for ordering costs K_{bpi} , K_{vs} , and K_{vri} and holding costs h_{boi} and h_v , while the buyers are responsible for ordering costs K_{bri} and holding costs h_{bsi} .
- 2) The vendor produces each cycle nQ units continuously throughout the first nt time units.
- 3) The vendor's production rate exceeds the total demand for all buyers; $P > D$.
- 4) Buyers receive the same number of orders, n , during each cycle.
- 5) A buyer, i , receives equal-size orders, q_i . However, different buyers receive different size orders based on their demand rates, where the q_i/d_i ratio is the same for all buyers.

- 6) A buyer, i , receives an order, q_i , and then this cycle is repeated until all orders are fulfilled, i.e., a cyclic shipping plan.
- 7) Buyers have an equal inspection rate, I_r , which is higher than the demand rate of any buyer; $I_r > d_i, \forall i$.
- 8) Buyers inspect all received items and consume only the accepted ones. While falsely accepted items are used to produce low-value items.
- 9) Buyers rejected items are discarded together at the end of the inspection process (Khan et al., 2014; Salameh and Jaber, 2000).
- 10) The inspection process is subjected to classification errors. Type I error, e_1 , in which the non-defective item can be classified as defective, and Type II error, e_2 , in which the defective item can be classified as non-defective, are shown in Table 10.
- 11) The percentage of defective items, p , and the probabilities of type I and type II errors, e_1 and e_2 , are given constants that represent the expected values of random variables with probability density functions $f(p)$, $f(e_1)$, and $f(e_2)$, respectively.

Table 10 Item classification after the inspection activity

		Item classification after inspection	
		Non-defective	Defective
Item true classification	Non-defective ($1-p$)	$(1-p)(1-e_1)$ Correctly accepted	$(1-p)(e_1)$ Falsely rejected Type I error
	Defective (p)	$(p)(e_2)$ Falsely accepted Type II error	$(p)(1-e_2)$ Correctly rejected

3.2. Inventory modeling

The stocking process starts with the vendor sending the first order to the first buyer, q_1 , and then the first order to the second buyer, q_2 , as depicted in Figure 3. After a period t , buyers receive the second order before depleting the first one. Consequently, the buyers' inventory buildup increases the holding cost. However, the buyer's inventory costs are charged to the vendor under the consignment policy partnership. Buyers' initial inventory after receiving an order is I_1 . After that, consumption and inspection processes start at rates of d_i and I_r , resulting in a reduction in inventory level, as shown in Figure 3. The inspection process removes the defective items, while the consumption process satisfies the demand for the non-defective items. The inventory level at the end of the cycle reaches I_4 before receiving the order.

Figure 3 Inventory profile for 1 vendor-2 buyers collaboration

As a result of buyers' inspection errors, the accepted and rejected items can be either defective or non-defective. So, the effective proportion of rejected items, p_e , is the correctly rejected items, $p(1 - e_2)$, and the falsely rejected items, $(1 - p)e_1$, Eq. (1). Consequently, just $q_i(1 - p_e)$ accepted units are consumed to fill an order, q_i . In addition, during a cycle, T , the number of used accepted items, $nq_i(1 - p_e)$, must satisfy the demand for buyer i , Td_i , Eq. (2). Eq. (3) represents mathematically the required time to produce an order for all buyers.

$$p_e = p(1 - e_2) + (1 - p)e_1 \quad (1)$$

$$T = \frac{nq_i(1 - p_e)}{d_i} = \frac{nQ(1 - p_e)}{D} \quad (2)$$

$$t = \frac{DT}{nP(1 - p_e)} \quad (3)$$

Referring to Figure 3, the average inventory of the vendor, \bar{I}_v , is calculated using the total area of the triangles, where the height is q_i and the base is q_i/P . Therefore, the total n triangular areas for each of the N buyers are divided by the cycle time T gives, so it can be formulated mathematically as follows:

$$\bar{I}_v = \frac{T}{2Pn(1 - p_e)^2} \sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2 \quad (4)$$

Contrarily, referring to Figure 3, the average inventory of a buyer equals the sum of the areas under the inventory profile divided by the cycle time, Eq. (5). The area is n pairs of trapezoids, Area 1 and Area 2, and at the end of the cycle, one triangle, TRI. After formulating the area and performing simplification, the mathematical expression in (6) can be used for the average inventory of a buyer.

$$\bar{I}_{b,i} = \frac{1}{T} \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^n Area\ 1_{i,j} + Area\ 2_{i,j} \right) + Area\ 3_i \right] \tag{5}$$

$$\bar{I}_{b,i} = \frac{d_i T}{2Pn(1-p_e)^2} \left[\alpha + \frac{2Pp_e d_i}{I_r} \right] \tag{6}$$

$$\alpha = (1-p_e)[D + n(P - Pp_e - D)] \tag{7}$$

where i is the buyer number, and j is the order number in the cycle

3.3. Mathematical model

The vendor is responsible for determining the order time and quantity, so the vendor's total cost has seven components, Eq. (8). The first three components are the vendor's setup cost, K_{vs} , shipment release cost, K_{vri} , holding cost, $h_v \bar{I}_v$. Under the consignment policy, the fourth and fifth components are buyers' ordering costs, nK_{bpi} , and holding costs, $h_{boi} \bar{I}_{b,i}$. Finally, the last two components formulate the cost of rejected items, either false or correct rejection.

$$TC_v(n, T) = \frac{K_{vs}}{T} + \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^N K_{vri}}{T} + h_v \frac{T}{2Pn(1-p_e)^2} \sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2 + \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^N K_{bpi}}{T} \tag{8}$$

$$+ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N h_{boi} d_i \left[\alpha + \frac{2Pp_e d_i}{I_r} \right]}{2Pn(1-p_e)^2} + \frac{c_{fr} D(1-p)e_1}{1-p_e} + \frac{c_{cr} Dp(1-e_2)}{1-p_e}$$

For each buyer, i, there are three cost components, Eq. (9): (1) cost of receiving orders, nK_{bri} , (2)

holding cost: the cost of physical storage per unit, h_{bsi} , times the average inventory level, \bar{I}_{bi} , and (3) cost of false acceptance of defective items: the cost of false acceptance per unit, c_{fa} , times the expected number of falsely accepted units. Adding the costs of the vendor and all buyers, Eqs. (8) and (9), the total cost for the supply chain system is expressed mathematically in Eq. (10).

$$TC_{bi}(n, T) = \frac{nK_{bri}}{T} + \frac{h_{bsi} d_i}{2Pn(1-p_e)^2} \left[\alpha + \frac{2Pp_e d_i}{I_r} \right] T + \frac{c_{fa} p e_2 d_i}{1-p_e} \tag{9}$$

$$TC(n, T) = \frac{K_{vs} + n \sum_{i=1}^N (K_{vri} + K_{bpi} + K_{bri})}{T} + \frac{D [c_{fr}(1-p)e_1 + c_{cr}p(1-e_2) + c_{fa}p e_2]}{1-p_e} \tag{10}$$

$$+ \frac{h_v \sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N (h_{boi} + h_{bsi}) d_i \left[\alpha + \frac{2Pp_e d_i}{I_r} \right]}{2Pn(1-p_e)^2} T$$

4. Solution approach

The total cost expressed in Eq. (10) is convex regarding the cycle time, T, since its second partial derivative with respect to T is positive for all $T > 0$. Differentiating Eq. (10) with respect to the number of cycles, n, and equating it to zero, the optimum cycle time, T, is obtained in Eq. (11). Then, Eq. (12) is derived by substituting the value of T into Eq. (10). In Eq. (12), the term under the square root should be minimized to minimize the total cost. This can be achieved by setting Term (n + 1) > Term(n), deleting redundant terms, and combining similar terms. Then, by getting the positive roots of the quadratic function, Eq. (13) expresses the optimum number of cycles.

$$T = \sqrt{\frac{2Pn(1-p_e)^2[K_{vs} + n\sum_{i=1}^N(K_{vri} + K_{bpi} + K_{bri})]}{h_v\sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N(h_{boi} + h_{bsi})d_i\left[\alpha + \frac{2Pp_e}{S_r}d_i\right]}} \quad (11)$$

$$TC(n, T) = \frac{D[c_{fr}(1-p)e_1 + c_{cr}p(1-e_2) + c_{fa}pe_2]}{1-p_e} + \sqrt{\frac{2[K_{vs} + n\sum_{i=1}^N(K_{vri} + K_{bpi} + K_{bri})]\left(h_v\sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N(h_{boi} + h_{bsi})d_i\left[\alpha + \frac{2Pp_e}{S_r}d_i\right]\right)}{Pn(1-p_e)^2}} \quad (12)$$

$$n = \sqrt{\frac{1 + 4K_{vs}\left[h_v\sum_{i=1}^N d_i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N(h_{boi} + h_{bsi})d_i\left(D - Dp_e + \frac{2Pp_e}{S_r}d_i\right)\right]}{4(1-p_e)(P - Pp_e - D)\left[\sum_{i=1}^N(h_{boi} + h_{bsi})d_i\right]\left[\sum_{i=1}^N(K_{vri} + K_{bpi} + K_{bri})\right]}} \quad (13)$$

In summary, the following steps are used to achieve the minimum total cost:

- 1- Determine the number of cycles, n , using Eq. (13). If n is not an integer, round it to the nearest lower integer $\lfloor n \rfloor$ and higher integer $\lceil n \rceil$.
- 2- Compute the total cost, $TC(n, T)$, for the values of n using Eq. (12). Then, choose the n value that yields the minimum total cost.
- 3- Substitute the optimum number of cycles, n , into Eq. (11) to calculate the optimum cycle length, T .

5. A numerical example and sensitivity analysis

A numerical example is presented to discuss the managerial aspects of the proposed model. The data for an SC with a single vendor and two buyers is adopted from the literature and listed in Table 11 (Ben-Daya et al., 2013; Khan et al., 2016).

Table 11 Numerical example data

$P = 3200$ units/year	$K_{bp1} = 15$	$S_r = 175,200$ units/year
$D = 1500$ units/year	$K_{bp2} = 50$	$f(e_1) = U(0, 0.04)$
$d_1 = 500$ units/year	$K_{br1} = 10$	$f(e_2) = U(0, 0.04)$
$d_2 = 1000$ units/year	$K_{br2} = 25$	$f(p) = U(0, 0.04)$
$h_{bo1} = \$2.5$ /unit/year	$h_v = \$4$ /unit/year	$c_{cr} = \$100$ /unit
$h_{bo2} = \$2$ /unit/year	$K_{vr1} = \$0$ /shipment	$c_{fr} = \$50$ /unit
$h_{bs1} = \$2.5$ /unit/year	$K_{vr2} = \$0$ /shipment	$c_{fa} = \$200$ /unit
$h_{bs2} = \$3$ /unit/year	$K_{vs} = \$400$ /setup	

Initially, the expected values of the inspection errors and percentage of defective items based on the given uniform distributions are ($p = 0.02$, $e_1 = 0.02$, $e_2 = 0.02$). Then, computing the number of shipments using Eq. (13), $n = 2.361$, and substituting both $\lfloor n \rfloor = 2$ and $\lceil n \rceil = 3$ into Eq. (12), the minimum total cost $TC = 7,511.59$ is associated with $n = 2$ and $T = 0.429$, as shown in Table 12.

Table 12 Solutions for vendor-buyer collaboration

n	t	T	q_1	q_2	TC_v	TC_{b1}	TC_{b2}	TC
1	0.161	0.33	172	343	6,815.17	278.1	654	7,747.25
2	0.105	0.429	112	223	6,534.01	291	686.6	7,511.59
3	0.081	0.499	87	173	6,470.47	312.2	738.6	7,521.27
4	0.068	0.556	72	145	6,467.79	333.9	791.9	7,593.60

This section provides a sensitivity analysis to gain managerial insights regarding vendor-buyer collaboration versus each party working individually. The cost functions of SC parties, Eqs. (8) and (9), are minimized in the same way as the total cost under collaboration is minimized, as shown in Table 13, Table 14, and Table 15. The results showed that the minimum SC cost of \$7,511.59 can be achieved if the vendor and buyers adopt a collaboration policy. This policy requires sacrifice from the SC parties, i.e., abandoning their minimum cost under individual behavior to reduce the system's total cost under the collaboration. The individual vendor minimum cost increases by 2.1% from 6,400.79 to 6,534.01. In addition, the cost of buyer 1 increases by 46% from 199.77 to 291.03, while the cost of buyer 2 increases by 46% from 470.66 to 686.55.

Table 13 Solutions if the vendor has chosen to work individually

n	t	T	q_1	q_2	TC_v	TC_{b1}	TC_{b2}	TC
1	0.212	0.434	226	451	6,734.17	335.8	791.8	7,861.80
2	0.138	0.566	147	295	6,461.39	344.6	814.1	7,620.12
3	0.107	0.657	114	228	6,401.42	364.4	862.5	7,628.26
4	0.089	0.729	95	190	6,400.79	385.4	913.9	7,700.11

Table 14 Solutions if buyer 1 has chosen to work individually

n	t	T	q_1	q_2	TC_v	TC_{b1}	TC_{b2}	TC
1	0.062	0.126	66	132	8,579.16	199.8	470.7	8,976.59
2	0.05	0.206	54	107	7,506.18	236.1	559.7	7,976.99
3	0.043	0.267	46	93	7,188.62	266.6	634.5	7,696.05
4	0.039	0.318	41	83	7,062.08	293.5	700.3	7,628.89

Table 15 Solutions if buyer 2 has chosen to work individually

n	t	T	q_1	q_2	TC_v	TC_{b1}	TC_{b2}	TC
1	0.063	0.129	67	134	8,511.72	199.8	470.7	9,059.86
2	0.051	0.21	55	109	7,461.31	236.1	559.6	8,032.91

3	0.044	0.272	47	94	7,151.23	266.7	634.4	7,816.72
4	0.04	0.324	42	84	7,028.32	293.5	700.1	7,768.73

6. Conclusions

This paper considers SCM in the context of vendor-buyer partnerships and item inspection on the buyer's side. The SC system comprises a vendor and multiple buyers who work under vendor-managed inventory and consignment stock policies. Two inspection errors were considered: accepting a defective unit and rejecting a good one. A mathematical model is formulated, and a solution approach is developed to minimize the total SC cost. Finally, a numerical example illustrates the solution procedure and the main benefits of vendor-buyer collaboration. While inspection errors significantly increase the costs of the SC parties, the impact is more substantial on the vendor's costs. The results showed that the minimum SC cost could be achieved under the collaboration policy. This policy requires abandoning the parties' minimum cost under individual behavior to reduce the system's total cost under collaboration. However, removing the main limitations of the adopted assumptions, such as the size, number, and sequence of shipments, represents promising research directions.

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